

SPIRAL OF SILENCE AND WORKPLACE HARASSMENT IN A PAKISTANI PUBLIC SECTOR ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

Modern organizations are structured to engage individuals in exchange for their skills and labor, with the ultimate aim of achieving defined institutional goals. However, beneath this formal arrangement lie complex and often troubling internal dynamics, including workplace harassment and exploitation. This qualitative study investigates the lived experiences of employees within a Pakistani public sector organization, focusing on the psychological and social impact of workplace harassment. Drawing on in-depth interviews with seven employees (five females and two males), the study reveals a consistent pattern of fear among victims—particularly the fear of social rejection, professional isolation, and retaliation from perpetrators. These fears contribute to a culture of silence, where individuals choose to endure mistreatment rather than risk the consequences of speaking out. The findings underscore the urgent need for effective organizational mechanisms to address harassment, protect victims, and promote a safer, more inclusive work environment.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations are structured groups which consist of interpersonal and intergroup relationships based on power, hierarchy, monetary gains and shared goals (Hogg & Terry, 2001). Nowadays, the aim of modern organizations is to employ people as an exchange for their skills which are then used to achieve particular goals. However, the internal workings of an organization are far from perfect with exploitation and harassment becoming a common occurrence in most organizations. Hence, harassment at the workplace results in employees suffering on a regular basis due to stress, humiliation and a fear of rejection from their colleagues (Salin, 2008). According to Vakola and Nikolaou (2005), stress at the workplace leads to decrease in job satisfaction, absenteeism, lack of

communication and poor performance. It also affects personal lives of employees as their personal relationships are also strained by the stress they bring home from work (Duffy & Sperry, 2007). Hence, the impact of harassment on an employee is profound and it tends to encompass their professional and personal spheres of life.

Numerous studies have focused on workplace harassment and its multiple types such as workplace bullying (Einarsen & Nielsen, 2015), workplace mobbing (Shallcross et al., 2008), sexual harassment (Shultz, 1998) and gender harassment (Leskinen et al., 2011) etc. However, in the case of Pakistan, comprehensive research on the actual experiences of workplace harassment is scarce. Therefore, it is important to understand workplace

harassment and its types through the words of those who have actually faced it. This approach would help in observing the phenomenon of workplace harassment in a local context. It is also pertinent to document the effects of workplace harassment on employees' lives. As mentioned above, it has been established that workplace harassment may exist in organizations and can adversely affect employees however this research is based on organizational communication therefore it focuses on whether employees communicate their ordeals to relevant persons or not. The purpose of communication can be to seek a solution to the problem or for catharsis and support seeking. However, Morrison and Milliken (2000) are of the view that employees avoid communicating experiences of harassment to others because of an uncooperative management, a hostile work environment, a fear of isolation from colleagues and fear of being the center of workplace gossip. This concept which is also called 'employee silence' is an umbrella term used to describe the reasons behind reluctance of employees to voice their opinions and experiences to others within the organization. (Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

Objectives

O1: To determine the perceived impact of workplace harassment on employees' work life.

O2: To understand whether the harassed employees experience fear of isolation or not.

Research Questions

RQ1: Do the harassed employees experience a fear of isolation at their workplace?

RQ2: Do the harassed employees keep silent or speak out to the senior management?

Harassment

Harassment is generally defined as hostility towards an individual due to his/her religion, sexual orientation, nationality, gender, race and disability (EEOC, 2016). The primary purpose of Harassment is to abuse, insult, demean, intimidate and embarrass an individual in order to cause stress and psychological harm (UNHCR, 2005). Examples of harassment broadly include academic and peer harassment (Eisenberg et al., 2003), workplace harassment (Salin, 2008) and sexual

harassment (Spector et al., 2014). Nowadays, contemporary forms of harassment such as cyber harassment and online bullying have also emerged thus indicating that harassment can take place anywhere and is not limited to a fixed location (Garbarino, 2002).

The causes of harassment are often complex and the types range from discrimination at a personal level to intimidation at group level (LSE, 2015). Moreover, repeated provocations by the harasser evoke feelings of fear, distress and vulnerability which are psychologically damaging to the victim and prevent them from living a normal life (Kath et al., 2009). The constant fear and stress faced due to harassment may also lead to suicide when the ordeal becomes unbearable for the victim. Therefore, anti-harassment policies have been passed at local as well as state level in most countries which strictly deal with multiple types of harassment (Zippel, 2004). Similarly, harassment and its types and causes have been extensively explored but workplace harassment has been the primary focus of researchers and is interchangeably used with the terms workplace sexual harassment (McDonald, 2012), workplace bullying (Einarsen et al., 2003) and workplace mobbing (Duffy, 2009). These different terms conceptualize a common aspect i.e. negative workplace interactions which affect the workforce and productivity of organizations.

Workplace Harassment

Overall, the term 'Workplace harassment' is defined as improper conduct of an employee towards another employee with the intention to cause offense or humiliation (UNDP, 2010). It includes hostile interactions accompanied by bullying and personal attacks that are conducted with the aim to humiliate a person and oust them from the workplace (Lewis et al., 2002). Workplace harassment may include verbal and physical aggression but it also mostly includes dirty gestures, silent treatment and mind games (Bowling & Beehr, 2006). According to Rospenda and Richman (2004), verbal and physical abuse along with manipulation are the most experienced forms of workplace harassment which in turn, play a

major role in creating a stressful unproductive environment for the victim.

Moreover, workplace harassment also includes job termination threats, salary decrement, cancellation of leaves and long work hours. Such abuse is common where the harasser is influential and is seeking to build a case against the victim with the intention to make them comply or leave the job. (Lutgen-Sandvik, 2003). Another important aspect of workplace harassment is its multidimensionality. It is not a completely top down or bottom up phenomenon because employees can harass their supervisors and coworkers can also harass each other too (Duffy, 2009). Hence, victims of workplace harassment constantly suffer from low self-esteem, depression and self-blaming. Their performance at work is badly affected and most of them are forced to leave the job when harassment becomes unbearable (Bowling & Beehr, 2006).

Workplace Bullying

Furthermore, along with the above-mentioned types of workplace harassment, contemporary definitions of the phenomenon also include 'workplace bullying' and 'workplace mobbing'. Workplace bullying has nearly the same definition as workplace harassment and the two terms are mostly used interchangeably but a key difference is that bullies may target more than one person regardless of the victim's ethnicity, gender, age or religion (Einarsen et al., 2011). Therefore, workplace bullying can occur to anybody regardless of them being male or female, young or old etc. According to Leymann and Gustafsson (1996), bullying of any form is fully comparable with Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) encountered by prisoners of war. This comparison indicates the extent of damage caused to the victim by workplace bullying. Therefore, bullying in the workplace has adverse effects on the victims heralding a loss of self-confidence, stress, depression, poor physical health and isolation from everyday activities (Vartia, 2001). Hence, as a result of the awareness created by scholars about the adverse effects of bullying, organizations are paying more attention to anti-bullying strategies and are investing in programs that educate employees about the effects of bullying. (Fox & Stallworth, 2009).

Workplace Mobbing

Similarly, along with workplace bullying, mobbing is a term that adds to the definition of workplace harassment. According to Duffy and Sperry (2007), workplace mobbing is a term used to explain the 'ganging up' of a group against an individual. It is defined as a form of harassment where there is collective effort of a group against a fellow colleague with the purpose to degrade, demean and ultimately oust that person from the workplace (Duffy, 2009). Mobbing also indicates the 'nonviolent mob mentality' of a group against an individual. The term 'Nonviolent' shows that the workplace mob harasses the person without actual use of physical violence in order to make the harassment difficult to detect (Gorlewski et al., 2014).

Moreover, employees who face mobbing at the hands of a group are exposed to intimidating behaviors such as destructive criticism, rumors, hurtful gossip, personal attacks and even physical assault. (de Pedro & Sanchez, 2008). Victims of mobbing also face a lot of hardships in reporting their ordeal especially when the groups that harass them are influential in the organization. (Harvey et al., 2006). Therefore, when victims find no relief from the constant mental torture, they either leave the job or commit suicide (Duffy, 2009). However, it is observed that mobbing may not just take place because of a group's aversion towards the victim. It also occurs when the perpetrator occupies an influential position with the organization or is the boss of the victim (Grover & Piro, 2010). Thus, the perpetrator uses that position to gather support from others. The primary reason for supporting the harasser can be to reap personal benefits and ensure the occurrence of promotions, bonuses and other perks. Overall the concepts of workplace harassment, workplace mobbing and workplace bullying point towards the hostile work environment and internal politics which permeate offices nowadays. It is a global issue that encompasses all organizations regardless of their geographical locations and differences in cultures and policies. (Shreck, 2011).

Spiral of Silence and Workplace Harassment

As discussed above, spirals of silence on different issues prevail in organizations. However in the case of workplace harassment, a spiral of silence is formed when the harassed employee fears getting singled out and isolated from fellow colleagues and staff. Moreover, the collective fears of being misunderstood, accused of wrongdoing or losing the job forces harassment victims to stay silent (Gul, 2012). Another dilemma which arises for harassment victims is that even if they break the silence, their plight is overlooked because the management wants to prevent a scandal from tarnishing the reputation of the organization. This happens in the case of workplace bullying/mobbing when the perpetrators hold a favorable image in front of the management (Harvey et al., 2006). Hence, it is very important that harassment victims receive support from their colleagues and bosses and are given the confidence to voice their ordeal because unless they are not given support, they would keep quiet and perceive themselves to be isolated and in minority. Keeping this aspect in view, some organizations provide support in the form of anti-harassment workshops and drives. These workshops and drives are pivotal in encouraging victims to break the spirals of silence and to share valuable insights on how to avoid harassment at the workplace. (Yamada, 2004).

Lastly, in the case of Pakistan, sexual harassment of females in organizations has been analyzed however extensive research on the relationship between spiral of silence and workplace harassment is practically nonexistent. Therefore, this research aims to fill the gap in the literature by determining the relationship between spiral of silence and workplace harassment at a Pakistani public sector organization. For this purpose, phenomenological approach has been utilized to document complete experiences of workplace harassment victims at a public sector organization. This approach seeks to determine 1) the experiences of workplace harassment faced by the employees 2) the perceived impact of harassment on their work lives 3) whether the harassed employees experience a fear of isolation at their workplace and 4) whether they keep silent or speak out to the senior management.

Fear of Social Isolation

People fear social rejection and avoid expressing their honest opinions if they feel it will socially isolate them from others (Neuwirth & Frederick, 2004). According to Noelle-Neumann (1993), fear of social isolation dictates the human tendency to gain acceptability amongst others therefore individuals shape their opinion according to their perception of the majority's opinion. Moreover, due to this fear of isolation, people refrain from expressing their opinion when they perceive that they would face harsh objections, destructive criticism and scorn or simply be made fun of by others (Noelle-Neumann & Peterson, 2004).

Presence of Vocal Minority

Another major criticism of the Spiral of Silence theory is that it overlooks the presence of a vocal minority which speaks out regardless of whether they perceive their views to be in the minority or not. Some people share their experiences regardless of the social or moral pressure they encounter therefore Spiral of Silence theory is not applicable to this minority and is not generalizable (Moy et al., 2001). Previous studies had documented the presence of vocal minority in political debates and election campaigns however due to the onset of information and communication technology, researchers have shifted their focus to online mediums of communication. Social networking sites such as Facebook and Twitter allow discussions on numerous topics pertaining to politics, religion and social issues. The presence of a vocal minority has been detected even in these online mediums. From charged political discussions on Twitter (Mustafaraj et al., 2011) to self-expression of LGBTQ+ communities on Facebook (Fox & Warber, 2015), vocal minorities speak out on controversial issues regardless of whether their opinion will be welcomed by the dominating majority or not. Therefore, the presence of a vocal minority leads to the inapplicability of Spiral of Silence theory in certain situations.

Yet, despite the differences in methodologies and criticism of the theory's postulates, researchers have established a fact that spiral of silence theory is applicable in issues that are controversial and have

a moral component attached to them (Hopkins, 2015). This is because silence exists when voicing an opinion on a controversial issue becomes difficult due to societal, professional or moral pressure. This concept can be applied to the phenomenon of workplace harassment and silence in organizations too.

Experiences of Workplace Harassment

The first research question aimed at exploring and understanding the experience of workplace harassment. According to one female interviewee Asma, there was not just one definite act of harassment committed by the perpetrator. Instead she, along with a group of colleagues, faced multiple types of harassment over a prolonged period of time.

Invitations to Parties and Dinner Dates

It all started off with winking of eyes, flattering compliments and invitations to dinner dates and liquor parties” said Asma while nervously observing her surroundings in case someone was there. “I was quite blunt so when he used to wink at me, I used to protest loudly that what are you trying to do, but this (behavior) didn’t stop”. On being asked if she was the only one who was at the receiving end of this behavior, Asma replied “No, it was happening with others too, when I was constantly given trouble (by these invitations) and when I talked to my female colleagues then I found out that they were also facing the same thing. They were getting the same invitations as me. These included talks of spending nights together, talks of dating and talks of drinking liquor”.

The invitations were not exclusive to one female only as it seemed the perpetrator had tried to use this strategy on multiple women. Another female interviewee Maria also mentioned the invitations to dinners and parties and how they became a source of great mental torture for her. “They (the perpetrator and his friend) said to me that we’ll party together, we’ll drink liquor and have fun. When I refused, he (the perpetrator) spread an image about me that I have an attitude problem”. The invitations to dinner became more forceful with time and the perpetrator began to pressurize and bully the female for her consent. “I kept getting

phone calls at night and once they even came to my house unannounced and said we are waiting for you come and join us for dinner”. On being asked about her reaction to the whole situation, Maria took a deep breath and said “I was so scared that I literally started shivering”.

Her colleague Fatima who also received unwanted invitations from the perpetrator further added “It was this pathetic mentality of the (perpetrator) that (he) expected us to get lured towards these things and he kept trying everywhere”. Another interviewee Amna was of the view that the perpetrator used the contract renewal process as a way to give unwanted dinner and hotel invitations to multiple females. She said “When our contracts used to go to his table for renewal at the end of the year then this mister used to say where we will meet, which hotel we will meet at and which restaurant we will go to.

Unwanted Physical Advances

Forceful invitations to dinner were just a tip of the iceberg for these women as the perpetrator’s actions became more malicious with time especially when he encountered resistance from them. By that time he had also started to make unwanted physical advances towards the females. “He tried to touch me... and that crossed all professional limits” said Asma while controlling her emotions. On being asked about whether they were subjected to unwanted physical contact, the female interviewees looked visibly uncomfortable and dodged the question. Another female interviewee Amna said “Physical...uhhh ... yes I was physically harassed” but she quickly changed the topic. However, Asma disclosed how a male colleague had saved this particular female from the perpetrator’s attempt at sexual harassment. “He (the perpetrator) was physically misbehaving with Amna in the corridor and when she shouted then Tariq (the male colleague) came out from his office but by that time the perpetrator had left. Then this woman told Tariq about the perpetrator’s attempt”.

Moreover, after some probing by the researcher, Maria explained how she managed to ward off constant demands for physical relations by the perpetrator and his friends. “I begged them (in a text message) that please let me work in peace, I

can't keep physical relations with anyone. It was after this message that they placed another option in front of me. The option was that convince a friend or a colleague, she can do all this with us, you're unmarried and can't do this so it is ok. But you can give us company in drinking liquor and wine. For the remaining (physical) stuff, we can convince someone else".

Work Related Exploitation

When Asma and her colleagues started to resist the perpetrator's demands, he began to bully and blackmail each of them by exercising his influential status. "He forcefully transferred all of us to another department, sometimes our salaries were cut, sometimes we were not allowed to perform our duties and inexperienced juniors were put in our place, even our contracts weren't renewed" said Asma while fidgeting with the strap of her purse. Her colleague, Maria further explained about the sudden salary decrement and tough duty hours she was forced to go through. "I was made to do such shifts that I was coming at night and then doing the consecutive night and morning shifts. And an odd hour shift is very difficult especially when one is doing it consecutively. And one other thing they did, when I came here they had made a deal with me about paying me wages from the extraordinary category which has more worth. When I didn't listen to them they started making and giving me checks of first degree while I had already got work experience. Not only that they illegally held my salary for five months and I felt like running away". It seemed that salary decrement and wage exploitation was a tactic used by the perpetrator to victimize any person regardless of their gender. A male interviewee, Ali also mentioned that despite his extensive experience, he was not paid well and the perpetrator kept him hired on minimum wage. "I had a work experience of three and a half years and still I was paid two or three thousand a month. What is this?" On being asked why he faced such a situation, he said "I sometimes feel that I was specifically targeted because I'm from Peshawar and a Pathan so yes I feel I was targeted on the basis of ethnicity. Also I wasn't deemed as part of his (the perpetrator's) group". Ali further explained his thoughts and said "He (the perpetrator) divided

everyone into categories and his favorites would get the top positions in the outstanding category. So they earned triple the amount."

Moreover, the long duty hours and salary decrement issue was also faced by Fatima their colleague. She said "(They) put me in the shift that didn't suit, they overburdened (me) and got a lot of work done from me in a specific salary. They didn't increase my salary for five years and they didn't renew my contract". After a pause she said "In 2012, I was terminated without any reason. No complaint, no charge sheet nothing. When the perpetrator realized I was not of his track then he got rid of me". Furthermore, a female interviewee Amna also expressed her frustration at the constant threat of job termination that she faced when she rejected the perpetrator's offers of friendship and dinners. "My colleagues and I feared that the termination letter would be handed to us at the gate but it was God's grace (that it didn't happen)".

An aspect worth mentioning is that even petty issues such as using the washroom and drinking water became a cause of intense harassment due to the harsh rules imposed by the perpetrator. A male interviewee Tariq described his experience as "If I'm working for at least three to four hours in a shift I may need to go to the washroom, I may even feel thirsty. But when I used to say that I have to go to the washroom, my supervisor used to reply that the boss hasn't given permission for that". He further explained "Even if I'm sitting at some computer and reading stuff related to my work, I would get the order that get up from here, you are not allowed to sit here. This is harassment". His point was supported by Maria who also mentioned how petty issues became a cause of stress and mental agony. She said "We used to be on duty for five hours and we felt thirsty and needed to drink water, but we were not allowed to go and drink water".

Perceived Impact of Harassment on Work Life

The second research question focused on the perceived impact of workplace harassment on the interviewees' work lives. Regarding this aspect, the female interviewee Asma was of the view that workplace harassment had an effect on her performance. She said "the nature of our job is such that we can't make mistakes. One has to be vigilant

and active. So there was a major pressure that I might make a mistake and that would be used as a basis to strengthen the case against us”.

Her colleague Maria talked about the personal difficulties she faced in her work life. “I was scared and it became difficult for me to perform, there was no confidence on my face. Survival was very hard because of lack of money and the fact that I and my colleagues were laid off for a month so you can imagine the extent to which our careers were in danger of getting damaged. All this trouble impacted me so much that I became silent and my colleagues asked me if I’m an introvert”.

Another female interviewee Saleha shared a similar view and explained about the stress she faced post harassment. According to her, every aspect of her performance and personality got damaged. She said “It seemed to me as if my brain had stopped working, I became so stressed that I had even made up my mind to leave the job. Even till now I have this thought in my mind. I have become so mentally disturbed because of this thing (harassment) and it is such a thing that one can’t tell everyone. And when one can’t tell everyone then that results in even more stress. My self-confidence had decreased to such an extent that when I used to do my work, I couldn’t even form the words in my mind. Such difficulty I had to witness. I lost trust in my abilities. I felt when I will open my mouth, I will speak wrong things. Mistake after mistake began to happen and with great difficulty I managed to pull myself together and regain my confidence”.

Furthermore, her colleague Amna explained the impact of workplace harassment on her health and her growing resentment towards the organization. She said “my health and performance was affected but more than that I was hurt that we are also part of the organization. I spent seven years here and Asma has been here for ten years and apart from Maria, everyone is senior to me but just because we’re women why didn’t anybody stand up for us?”. However, her fellow workmate Fatima shared a different point of view regarding the impact of workplace harassment on her work life. In a confident tone she said “Work performance was not affected. In fact after such experiences, I started working with more enthusiasm. But of course I was tense. Umm I did face a lot of stress I remember

clearly. It was a temporary phase and thank God it is over”.

Similarly, the two male interviewees held different opinions regarding the impact of harassment on their work lives. In reply to the question regarding impact, Tariq described how his work life was affected and how it further impacted his personal life. He said “Obviously there is an effect. Performance is affected. Concentration is affected along with self-esteem too. One is unable to feel comfortable at the workplace. The stress effects personal life and personal relationships also spoil because of it, so yes there is a very negative impact”. When the researcher asked Tariq what else he was feeling due to the impact of harassment on his work life, he replied darkly “I was feeling very desperate. I felt like....ummm... I wanted to hit him (the perpetrator) hard and it was quite possible that it could’ve happened”.

However, his fellow coworker Ali expressed indifference to the harassment he faced at work. He said “I’m strong thanks to Allah, I wasn’t allowed to move forward so I was a bit late in learning (about my field) but now thanks to Allah I’m on a good level. Nothing happened to me because I’m a strong person by nature”.

Conclusion:

Spiral of Silence theory has been pivotal in aiding researchers to understand the formation of a climate of opinion and its influence on individual opinions. It has been applied to numerous studies to determine the factors which prevent people from expressing their honest viewpoints when faced with a majority opinion on any issue. Moreover, this theory has been applied to study opinion expression on issues that are controversial in nature or have a moral component attached. Therefore, this research follows the same pattern and explores workplace harassment in the context of Spiral of Silence theory by analyzing real life experiences of harassment victims in a Pakistani public sector organization. For this purpose, transcendental phenomenology is used to accurately document the experiences without any personal bias of the researcher.

Based on the experiences shared by interviewees, it can be concluded that workplace harassment is a

serious problem because it is not limited to a few specific types. In fact, vulnerable victims are subjected to multiple types of harassment by the perpetrator depending upon the situation. Moreover, the extent of damage caused by harassment depends upon the position occupied by the perpetrator within the organization. When the perpetrator is influential then this influence gives rise to more problems such as lack of cooperation of the management and formation of a group of people who are in favor of the perpetrator etc. Also, work related exploitation such as contract termination, salary cuts, consecutive shifts and a very heavy workload are common strategies used by the perpetrator to create pressure on victims to comply with his unjust demands. When the victims constantly face such harrowing experiences then it affects their personal lives and personal relationships. Plus their health and work performance also suffers due to stress and anxiety.

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